

Fabrication and surface stochastic analysis of enhanced photoelectrochemical activity of tuneable MoS₂-CdS thin film heterojunction

M. Zirak,^a M. Ebrahimi^a, M. Zhao^b, O. Moradlou^c, M. Samadi^a, A. Bayat^a, H.L. Zhang^{*b}, and A. Z. Moshfegh^{*ad}

Abstract

A very simple and well-controlled procedure was employed to prepare CdS nanoparticles/few-layer MoS₂ nanosheets/Indium tin oxide (ITO) thin film heterostructures. To tune and fabricate the CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films with various surface topographies, at first the electrophoretic deposition (EPD) was used to deposit MoS₂ nanosheets on ITO substrate under the optimized applying potential (8V) for different deposition times (*t*) of 30, 60, 120 and 240 s. Then, CdS nanoparticles were deposited via successive ion layer adsorption and reaction (SILAR) technique. The highest photo-current density of 285 μA/cm² was measured for CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO sample which was about 2.3 times higher than the value obtained for bare CdS/ITO. The photo-enhancement mechanism of the CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO heterostructures was described using a stochastic model. The results showed that the CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO electrode exhibited the highest roughness exponent ($2\alpha=0.67$) with the smoothest nanometric fluctuations resulting in the best wetting property, the highest interaction between the electrolyte and the sample surface leading to the highest PEC activity. On the other hand, the samples with small α possess rough and nanometric-jagged fluctuations. The air trapping inside these microscopic surface fluctuations reduces the wettability as well as surface interaction between the sample and the electrolyte, resulting in low photo-current density.

^a Department of Physics, Sharif University of Technology, P.O. Box 11555-9161, Tehran, Iran.

^b State Key Laboratory of Applied Organic Chemistry, College of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Lanzhou University, Lanzhou 730000 (P. R. China).

^c Department of Chemistry, Alzahra University, P.O. Box: 1993893973, Tehran, Iran

^d Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, Sharif University of Technology, P.O. Box 14588-8969, Tehran, Iran.

1. Introduction

In recent years, accompanying the fascinating properties of graphene and its booming development, growing research interest and scientific attention has been focused on the other ultrathin 2D crystals. In particular, there is at present an increasing interest in transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) due to their potentials for a wide range of applications.¹⁻³ TMDs have general formula of X-M-X (M is a transition metal such as Mo, W, Ti, V, and X is a chalcogen such as S and Se.) which two hexagonally-arranged X planes are separated by a same hexagonal metal plane. Inside each X-M-X layer, the atoms are bonded together covalently and adjacent layers stack over each other via weak van der Waals force.⁴ This weak interlayer force allows to easily exfoliating the bulk TMDs form into atomically thick 2D nanosheets. These 2D crystals can improve the intrinsic properties of their bulk form and introduce a completely new and fascinating range of properties.

Of particular interest, 2D-MoS₂ (the most famous and abundant member of TMDs) nanosheets have exhibited unique properties and applications such as hydrogen evolution reaction,⁵⁻⁷ nonlinear optical applications,^{2, 8} field effect transistor,^{9, 10} high performance Li and sodium ion batteries,¹¹⁻¹³ photoluminescence and bioimaging¹⁴ applications.

It has been reported that MoS₂ low dimensional nanostructures exhibit photo-responsivity due to their suitable band gap for solar spectrum absorption (MoS₂ mono-layer is a direct band gap semiconductor with energy band gap of $E_g \sim 1.9$ eV¹⁵) and photocatalytic stability against photocorrosion.^{16, 17} Numerous efforts have reported the photocatalytic activity of MoS₂ nanostructures toward water pollutant degradation,^{18, 19} photocatalytic hydrogen production^{20, 21} and photoelectrochemical activity,¹⁷ indicating promising potentials of MoS₂ 2D-nanosheets for solar energy harvesting and conversion.

Among various photo-active materials, CdS is subject of many interests because of its low cost and simple preparation methods for various applications.^{19, 22} More importantly, CdS has a narrow direct band gap with $E_g = 2.4$ eV,²³ making it a well-known photo-active material under visible light. However, bare CdS suffers from low photocatalytic activity and low stability under sunlight irradiation. To overcome these drawbacks, noble metal co-catalysts such as Pt, Pd, and Au are often used to improve its catalytic activity and stability.^{24, 25} But, using noble metal co-catalyst is limited due to their high cost and scarcity.

So, it is very interesting to find a low cost but effective alternative co-catalyst to improve CdS visible photo-activity and its stability against photocorrosion.

Recently, MoS₂ nanostructures have been shown as a promising low cost co-catalyst to enhance CdS photocatalytic activity toward hydrogen production.²⁵⁻²⁸ Zong et al. have experimentally confirmed that photocatalytic activity of MoS₂-loaded CdS is even higher than that of Pt/CdS under the same reaction conditions.^{25, 29} Chen et al. have also obtained H₂ evolution rate up to 1315 μmol h⁻¹ using the MoS₂/CdS photocatalyst which was much higher than 488 μmol h⁻¹ which was reported for Pt/CdS photocatalyst.²⁶

Although many fascinating photocatalytic results have been reported for MoS₂-CdS hetero-structure, but, low-cost, easy and safe preparation method to obtain MoS₂-CdS thin films and their photoelectrochemical (PEC) performance has been rarely investigated, and the PEC property of the MoS₂-CdS thin film is still in its infancy. Specially, to the best of our knowledge, the effect of MoS₂-CdS thin film topography on its PEC performance has not been reported yet.

We have demonstrated in our recent reports that investigation of surface topography from a stochastic point of view, provides very useful information to understand various properties of prepared thin films such as field emission property³⁰ and PEC performance.^{31, 32} Herein, for the first time, we have carefully explored the correlation between stochastic topographic properties and PEC performance of CdS/MoS₂/ITO thin films. To do that, we employed a facile, well-controlled, completely safe and straight forward procedure to prepare CdS/MoS₂ thin films on indium tin oxide (ITO) substrate with tuneable surface topographies. At the end, a mechanism was suggested based on the surface stochastic analysis and contact angle (CA) measurements. The proposed model can provide guidance to prepare the CdS/MoS₂/ITO thin film with specific surface topography and proper wettability leading to the highest PEC performance toward hydrogen production under sunlight irradiation.

2. Experimental and Methods

Materials

Deionized water purified with Milli-Q System (Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA) was used during all preparation procedures. All other materials were commercially provided and used without any further purification. These are including: absolute ethanol (Rionlon Chemical Reagent Inc., China), Indium tin oxide (ITO) sheets ($30 \Omega/\square$), bulk MoS₂ powder (1–6 μm diameter, Aladdin Reagent Inc., China), sodium sulphide (Na₂S·9H₂O, 98%, Tianjin Guangfu Fine Chemical Institute, China), cadmium nitrate (Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O, 99%, Beijing Chemical Reagent Research Institute, China).

Few-layer MoS₂ Solution Preparation

Based on our previous report,³³ mixed-solvent strategy was used to prepare few-layer MoS₂ solution. In brief, 250 mg of bulk MoS₂ was dispersed into 50 mL mixed water:ethanol solution with the volume fraction of water/ethanol=55/45. After 30 min stirring, the solution was sonicated for 15h in a common bath sonicator. The sonicated solution was maintained in room condition for 48h. Then, the 2/3 of the supernatant of the solution was collected and centrifuged at 3800 rpm for 45 min.

Thin Film Preparation

Electrophoretic deposition method was employed to deposit MoS₂ nanosheets. Two pre-cleaned ITO sheets were placed in parallel manner with distance of 15 mm inside the few-layer MoS₂ solution. The optimized electrical potential of 8V was applied between these two ITO electrodes for different deposition times (t) namely 30, 60, 120, and 240 s. After the preparation of MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films, the CdS nanoparticles were deposited on the layers via successive ion layer adsorption and reaction (SILAR) method. The layers were immersed into 50 mM Cd(NO₃)₂ and then in 50 mM Na₂S aqueous solutions for 20s. These two immersion steps were named as a SILAR cycle. The samples were rinsed with DI water between each immersion step. 20 SILAR cycles were repeated to obtain CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films.

PEC Measurements

The PEC results were obtained by using a three-electrode setup connected to a CHI 660D electrochemical workstation (Shanghai Chenhua Instrument Co., China). In this setup, the synthesized CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films were used as working electrode, a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode and a platinum wire as the counter electrode. All the electrodes were put into 50 mM Na₂S aqueous solution as electrolyte and 0.1 V bias voltage was applied during all PEC tests. The same electrolyte was also used to carry out the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements with the AC voltage amplitude of 5 mV and the voltage frequency ranging from 100 kHz to 1 Hz.

Surface Stochastic Analysis

Surface stochastic analysis was used for the better understanding of the surface topography effects on PEC activities of the samples. Most common concepts for stochastic study of a surface (two dimensional substrate of size L×L) are the mean height of growing film, \bar{h} , its surface roughness, W and roughness exponent, α defined by the following expressions:³⁶

$$\bar{h}(L, t) = \frac{1}{L^2} \int h(\vec{x}, t) d^2x \quad (1)$$

$$W(L, t) = \left(\langle [h - \bar{h}]^2 \rangle \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

where t and \vec{x} are the deposition time and lateral coordinate, respectively. The averaging over different realizations of the sample position is represented by notation of $\langle \dots \rangle$.

Surface structure function, $S(\vec{r})$, is used to measure the roughness exponent of a surface. This function depends on the length scale of $\Delta\vec{x} = \vec{r}$ and is defined as:³⁵

$$S(\vec{r}) = \langle |h(\vec{x} + \vec{r}) - h(\vec{x})|^2 \rangle \quad (3)$$

Height-height correlation function for a stationary surface, $C(r)$, is related to the surface structure function as follows:

$$S(r) = 2W^2(1 - C(r)) \quad (4)$$

$C(r)$ is defined by the correlation length η and the roughness exponent α (Hurst exponent) as is shown below:³⁵

$$C(r) = \exp\left(-\frac{r}{\eta}\right)^{2\alpha} \quad (5)$$

Replacing Eq. 5 into Eq. 4 and expand it for small r , the second order structure function $S(r)$ scales with r as following:³⁵

$$S(r) \sim r^\alpha \quad (6)$$

The roughness exponent α normally ranges between 0 and 1 ($0 < \alpha < 1$), and it is defined within the context of a microscopic limit ($L \rightarrow 0$). According to Eq. (5), for times much larger than saturation time, smaller roughness exponent corresponds to a very rough and jagged surface (high microscopic fluctuation). On the other hand, a surface with the larger roughness exponent possesses a smoother texture.^{30, 37} More information and detailed discussions about these parameters can be found elsewhere.³⁶ These concepts will be used to correlate the variation of surface roughness's and topographies of the deposited thin films and generated photo-current densities from the CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films during PEC process.

3. Results and Discussion

Exfoliated MoS₂ Nanosheets

Fig. 1 shows the UV-visible absorption spectrum of the MoS₂ few-layer solution. Obvious absorption peaks can be seen which are labelled as A, B, C and D peaks. A and B located at 676 and 619 nm, are excitonic transitions arising from spin-orbit splitting of K point of the Brillouin zone at the top of valence band (VB).¹⁵ C and D excitonic peaks located at 450 and 400 nm are related to interband transitions from the occupied dz^2 orbital to unoccupied dxy , x^2-y^2 and dxz , yz orbitals.¹⁷

It is clear that absorption of MoS₂ nanosheets increases from 800 to 400 nm (visible solar region) and decrease in UV region (400 to 200 nm), which indicates that MoS₂ flakes are very good candidates for photovoltaic and photocatalytic application in visible region of solar spectrum. In the photovoltaic related studies, sun light transmission is also an important parameter which determines the output photocurrent density of the materials. Therefore, the corresponding UV-Vis transmittance of the obtained MoS₂ solution has also been depicted in **Fig. S1** of electronic supplementary information (ESI). The absorption spectrum and light-brownish colour of the exfoliated solution (**Fig. 1, inset**) are in good agreement with standard UV-visible absorption spectrum for 2H-MoS₂ semiconducting phase,^{17, 38} indicating that no crystal change occurred during our proposed preparation procedure. AFM analysis was employed to explore the dimensions of the final MoS₂ flakes. A 2D-AFM image has been shown in **Fig. 2a** and height profiles of some selected flakes have been also plotted. As it can be seen, there is a distribution of flakes' size between about 30 and 150 nm and the thicknesses of flakes have distribution between about 1 and 15 nm. Herein, the obtained MoS₂ nanosheets which were obtained via mixed-solvent strategy (a category of sonication exfoliation) have the same behaviour too. The average thickness and lateral dimensions of the flakes are ~5 and ~ 60 nm, respectively.

Fig. 1

It is estimated that the prepared MoS₂ flakes contain 6 layers in average. It is worth to note that there are also many single-layer nanosheets in the final solution. The population of these single-layer flakes can be increased via higher speed centrifugation and appropriate filtrations. The dimensions of the flakes were also investigated through direct observation via TEM analysis. The TEM image (**Fig. 2b**) clearly shows the MoS₂ nanosheets with an average of 60 nm in size, confirming our AFM results. These results indicate that our utilized method can be manipulated to obtain both few-layer and single-layer MoS₂ nanosheets.

Fig. 2

CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films

Fig. 3 shows the UV-visible transmittance spectra of the thin films. As it can be seen, all of the CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films have lower transmittance than the bare CdS/ITO as it was expected. The CdS/ITO thin film has an absorption edge of ~500 nm. The bulk CdS thin film exhibits an absorption edge at 520 nm.⁴³ Thus, the observed blue-shift indicates that the obtained CdS/ITO thin films contains CdS nanostructures with the average dimension of ~ 10 nm.^{43, 44} A second absorption edge appears at ~680 nm in CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin film which it is absent in bare CdS/ITO layer. This absorption edge is related to peak A as excitonic transition in 2H-MoS₂ layer as discussed before (see [section 3.1](#) and **Fig. 1**). Inspecting the **Fig. 3** indicates that the addition of MoS₂ few-layer nanosheets to the CdS/ITO thin film increases the light intensity absorption and extends the absorption edge from 500 nm to ~700 nm, which are in favour of CdS thin film photo-activity enhancement under visible light. Similar observations have been reported elsewhere for CdS-MoS₂⁴⁵ and CdS-WS₂ heterostructures.⁴⁶

Fig. 3

Fig. 4a shows the Raman spectrum of the CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO thin film. Two obvious Raman peaks at 300 and 600 cm⁻¹ are related to two characteristic CdS longitudinal optical (LO) phonon modes named 1LO and 2LO, respectively.^{47, 48} The 1LO phonon peak for a single crystal of bulk CdS has been reported at peak position of 305 cm⁻¹, while it has been observed at ~ 300cm⁻¹ for CdS nanostructures.^{49, 50} It is well known that there are four active first-order Raman modes observed in bulk 2H-MoS₂ Raman spectra, namely, E_{1g} (286 cm⁻¹), E_{2g}¹(383 cm⁻¹), A_{1g} (407.5 cm⁻¹), and E_{2g}¹(32 cm⁻¹).^{52, 53} The E_{1g} mode is forbidden in the back scattering configuration. The MoS₂ Raman spectrum is dominated by E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} modes. These two peaks are clearly observable at 383.5 and 407.2 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of 2H-MoS₂ few layers in the final thin films. Using A_{1g} peak position, the following exponential fitting model can be used to estimate the average number of layers:

$$\omega_{A_{1g}}(N) = \omega_{bulk} + (\omega_{1L} - \omega_{bulk}) \exp[-\chi(N - 1)] \quad (7)$$

where N is the number of layers, χ the fitting parameter and $\omega_{bulk} = 407.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\omega_{1L} = 403 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are bulk, mono-layer and measured A_{1g} peak position of MoS_2 , respectively. After fitting the model to the data reported for various MoS_2 thicknesses,⁵³⁻⁵⁵ $\chi = 0.508$ was obtained. Inserting this parameter into the exponential fitting model, the average number of layers for $w = 407.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was estimated to be ~ 6 layers.

Fig. S2 shows the Raman mapping images, obtained for $\text{CdS}(1\text{LO})$ and $\text{MoS}_2(A_{1g})$ Raman signal in $\text{CdS}/\text{MoS}_2(60\text{s})/\text{ITO}$ sample. 2D flakes obtained by the proposed methods have a thickness and lateral dimension distribution as reported previously for other thin films,^{39-41, 56} and as expected, the obtained Raman mapping images for the synthesized samples do not have the same colour in different area.

The SEM images of bare ITO, MoS_2/ITO , CdS/ITO and $\text{CdS}/\text{MoS}_2(60\text{s})/\text{ITO}$ electrodes are included in ESI, **Fig. S3**. Comparing all the samples with bare ITO, confirms the complete and nearly uniform deposition of materials (CdS and MoS_2) on the substrate surface which is in agreement with Raman mapping results.

TEM analysis was used to clearly verify the formation of atomic-heterojunction between the CdS nanoparticles and MoS_2 nanosheets. The results have been shown in **Fig. 4b** and **c**. **Fig. 4b** shows that the CdS nanoparticles with an average diameter of $\sim 10 \text{ nm}$ have been deposited on the MoS_2 sheets, confirming Raman and UV-visible absorption results.

Fig. 4

The measured sizes of the deposited CdS nanoparticles are also in good agreement with our previous reports on CdS nanoparticles obtained via SILAR methods.^{43, 44} The hexagonal arrangement of atoms in MoS_2 nanosheets as well as the CdS (112) planes can be clearly observed in **Fig. 4c**.

Raman and TEM results strongly confirm that we have successfully fabricated $\text{CdS}-\text{MoS}_2$ atomic hetero-junction, using our simple combined procedure without any crystal changes and any oxidation.

Fig. 5 shows the measured J ($\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$) as a function of irradiation time (J - t curve). It was found that all the $\text{CdS}/\text{MoS}_2(t)/\text{ITO}$ thin films except $\text{CdS}/\text{MoS}_2(240\text{s})/\text{ITO}$ have higher photo-current densities as compared with the bare CdS/ITO layer ($125 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$). The

sample that was prepared with 30 s of MoS₂ deposition showed a higher J value (197 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$) as compared to the bare CdS/ITO. Further increasing MoS₂ deposition time to 60 s, resulted in increase of J up to 285 $\mu\text{A/cm}^2$. This is about 2.3 times greater than the value for the bare CdS/ITO thin film.

Fig. 5

The results show that charge separation and transfer condition is improved when CdS makes an appropriate junction with MoS₂ nanosheets. Accordingly, the rise and fall times of CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO and CdS/ITO was measured and the results have been shown and compared in Fig. S4. Rise times were determined to be 180 \pm 10 ms and 210 \pm 10 ms, and the fall times were obtained to be 300 \pm 10 ms and 380 \pm 10 ms for CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO and CdS/ITO, respectively. The shorter rise and fall times in CdS-MoS₂ sample show that the photo-sensitivity of CdS layer is improved when a junction is made with MoS₂ nanosheets, which is very beneficial for many application such as photo-detectors and sensors.⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰

Photoactivation Mechanism

Herein, for the first time, we have investigated the PEC performance of the CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films from surface stochastic and topographical point of view, accompanying with other important factors concerning. The R_{ct} values are extracted by fitting the Nyquist plots data with equivalent Randles circuit via Zview software, and the obtained values have been listed in Table 1. As it can be seen, deposition of MoS₂ nanosheets initially reduced the charge transfer resistance of the CdS/ITO thin films. But, increasing the EPD time resulted in increase in the MoS₂ loading, and consequently, the R_{ct} in CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films was increased as it was expected. Lower R_{ct} in CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films with t= 30 and 60 s as compared with CdS/ITO layer is a good reason for the obtained higher photo-current density.

2D-like structure of few-layer MoS₂ has very high surface area. So, it is expected that MoS₂ deposition increases the surface area of CdS layer and all the CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films have more surface area as compared with the CdS/ITO sample. MoS₂ deposition for 30 s resulted in slightly increase of rms surface roughness from 6.6 nm in the CdS/ITO to 7.1

nm for CdS/MoS₂(30s)/ITO. But the deposition of MoS₂ for 60 s significantly increased the surface roughness to 20.1 nm which is about 3 times greater than the bare CdS/ITO thin film. Longer deposition of MoS₂ for t > 60 s reduced the surface roughness from 20.1 nm for the CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO sample to 19.5 and 17 nm for the CdS/MoS₂(120s)/ITO and CdS/MoS₂(240s)/ITO thin films, respectively.

The obtained highest photo-current density (J) for the highest surface roughness (W) is reasonable. The CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO and CdS/MoS₂(120s)/ITO samples have nearly the same value of W in the range of our data error bar (± 0.5 nm), but the former photo-current density is much higher than the latter one. The obtained higher R_{ct} for the CdS/MoS₂(120s)/ITO is one of the reasons for its lower J. Concerning only R_{ct}, when charge transfer resistance of the CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO increased from 1467 Ω and reached to 2155 Ω in CdS/MoS₂(120s)/ITO, the J should be decreased from 285 to 194 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$.

The mechanism of enhanced PEC activity of the samples can be proposed as following: Interface state effect plays an important role in the heterojunction properties, and makes a crucial effect on photovoltaic, photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical properties of CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films. The nature and properties of interface of the materials influence on the charge separation and transport and consequently, on the photo-current density (J) of photo-active materials, and the authors are aware about interface states effects. therefore, J can be assumed as a function of interface states and morphology of the samples.

The interface states influence on charge resistance (R_{ct}) and the morphology can affect the contact angle (θ) and wettability of the thin films surfaces. The θ is itself a function of macroscopic fluctuation (which is concerned by surface roughness (W)) and microscopic fluctuation (denoted by Hurst exponent (α)). Therefore, it can be written:

$$J(\text{Interface state, Morphology})=J(R_{ct},\theta) \quad (7)$$

$$\theta=\theta(W,\alpha) \quad (8)$$

$$J(R_{ct},\theta)= J(R_{ct},W,\alpha) \quad (9)$$

The effect of surface morphologies of the samples, namely W and α , should be investigated. Based on discussions mentioned about W, for the samples with the same R_{ct} and W, the photo-current density is a function of Hurst exponent (α):

$$J(R_{ct}, W, \alpha) \sim J(\alpha) \quad (10)$$

Therefore, in the following we have discussed about relation between J and α . The macroscopic parameter W , microscopic parameter α and corresponding CA pictures for various CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin films have been illustrated together in Fig. S6. As it can be seen, among all of the samples prepared with various EPD times, the sample possessing the highest roughness exponent, exhibits the lowest contact angle and better wettability. The obtained CA results confirm our discussion, and the results can be explained by a simple mechanism illustrated in **Fig. 6**.

Fig. 6

According to the proposed mechanism for the CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO surfaces, (the resistance (R) and macroscopic fluctuations (W) were assumed to be constant), as the roughness exponent (α) increases, the microscopic fluctuations decreases results in a smoother surface in nanometric scale, the smaller contact angle and finally the larger surface contact between the electrolyte and the sample surface. This situation facilitates the photo-generated charge transfers into the electrolyte and as a result, the photocurrent density reaches to a greater value. On the other hand, the samples with smaller Hurst exponent (α) have rough and nanometric jagged fluctuations more than others.

To be more assure about the air trapping, the photo-current density of the CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO was measured under long time photo-irradiation. If the air trapping is occurred, the air molecules can be detrapped gradually during long time irradiation, increasing microscopic contact surface between the samples and the electrolyte, resulting in increase in the photocurrent density. The results have been shown in **Fig. S7**. As it can be seen, the generated photo-current density increases gradually during continuous photo-irradiation, which can be a sign of air detrapping. All of these obtained results are fully agreed with our proposed model.

4. Conclusions

We have reported a facile and well-controlled procedure to prepare CdS/MoS₂(t)/ITO thin film heterostructures with enhanced photo-current densities as compared with the bare CdS/ITO thin film. Our utilized experimental procedure allowed us to easily tune and prepare thin film heterojunctions with various surface topographies. To understand the role of surface parameters influencing the generated photo-current densities of the samples, the macroscopic (surface roughness W and surface area A_r) as well as microscopic surface properties (Hurst exponent α) were investigated, and we have found a correlation between these two scales using stochastic AFM observations. According to the stochastic data analysis, contact angle measurements and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements, it was shown that the samples with the higher roughness exponents have a smoother surface in nanometric scale resulting in a better wettability (lower contact angle) and higher photo-current density. On the other hand, the layers formed with small α values, have very rough and nanometric-jagged fluctuations which cause air trapping and reduce the wettability of the surface leading to the photo-current density reduction. Our stochastic investigation results provide very useful information to manipulate the surface topographic properties which influence the PEC performance of various photo-active thin films.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Table 1

Sample	Surface Ratio (A_r)	R_{ct} (Ω)	J ($\mu A/cm^2$)	Hurst exponent (2α)	Contact Angle ($^\circ$)
CdS/ITO	1.02 ± 0.02	2365 ± 70	125 ± 4	0.33 ± 0.03	91 ± 3
CdS/MoS₂(30s)/ITO	1.03 ± 0.01	1144 ± 35	197 ± 6	0.42 ± 0.02	83 ± 1
CdS/MoS₂(60s)/ITO	1.11 ± 0.01	1467 ± 50	285 ± 8	0.67 ± 0.04	68 ± 3
CdS/MoS₂(120s)/ITO	1.15 ± 0.03	2155 ± 70	177 ± 5	0.58 ± 0.03	83 ± 2
CdS/MoS₂(240s)/ITO	1.06 ± 0.02	3317 ± 110	105 ± 4	0.57 ± 0.02	85 ± 2